

AUTOMATIC MINUTES SUMMARIZATION IN INDICO USING AN OPEN-SOURCE LARGE LANGUAGE MODEL

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The objective of this project was to implement a plugin for **Indico**, CERN's open-source event management platform, that automatically generates summaries of meeting minutes using open-source large language models (LLMs). The plugin was intended to reduce the manual workload of post-meeting documentation by integrating AI-driven summarization directly into the Indico workflow.

- Objectives

- Evaluate different open-source LLMs (small, large, and quantized) with respect to output quality, inference time, and usability.
- Develop a proof-of-concept Indico plugin prototype capable of requesting and displaying automatically generated summaries.

- Scope

Included: Plugin development, backend–frontend integration, testing of multiple LLMs, human-based evaluation of summaries.

Excluded: Automatic metric evaluation (e.g., ROUGE/BLEU), and full-scale production deployment of large models beyond proof of concept.

- Requirements

Functional Requirements:

- Allow users to select meetings and trigger summarization directly from Indico.
- Support prompt customization for flexible summarization outputs.
- Display results as structured summaries in the Indico interface.

Non-Functional Requirements:

- Ensure reasonable inference times (under 1 minute for typical meeting notes)
- Provide readable and consistent summaries across different meeting types.
- Maintain modular design to allow independent updates to summarization models.

- Constraints

- **Time:** 9-week internship duration.
- **Resources:** Limited access to GPU resources; reliance on CPU and quantized models during early stages.

ABSTRACT

This project presents a plugin developed for Indico, CERN’s open-source event management platform, designed to automatically summarize meeting minutes using large language models (LLMs). The goal is to reduce the manual effort of post-meeting documentation by leveraging open-source, efficient, and accurate AI models. The plugin integrates directly into the Indico interface, enabling users to generate structured summaries by selecting meetings, editing prompts, and receiving results.

A range of open-source LLMs were evaluated, from lightweight models to large quantized ones, based on output quality, accuracy, inference time, and consistency. While smaller models proved insufficient, more powerful quantized models deployed via llama.cpp and eventually a GPU-backed model on CERN’s Kubeflow infrastructure achieved significantly better results. Human evaluations were used to assess summary quality and inform model selection.

The outcome is a working prototype capable of producing clear and concise summaries, laying the foundation for future improvements such as automatic metric-based evaluation, support for more complex prompts, and context-aware summarization.

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1 Introduction

This project focuses on developing a plugin for **Indico**[10], CERN's[2] open-source event and meeting management platform, to automatically generate summaries of meeting minutes using an **open-source Large Language Model (LLM)**.

Manual summarization of meetings is time-consuming, error-prone, and inconsistent. The goal is to streamline this process by integrating LLMs directly into Indico's user interface, enabling users to generate accurate, readable summaries.

LLMs are transformer-based neural networks trained on massive datasets to comprehend and generate human-like text. They enable a wide range of natural language processing tasks, including translation, summarization, question answering, and content generation[15].

While closed-source models such as GPT-4[7] demonstrate strong performance, they also present limitations, including restricted transparency, limited reproducibility, and dependency on proprietary third-party services. In contrast, open-source LLMs, such as LLaMA[13] or Gemma[5], promote transparency, facilitate community-driven development, and offer greater adaptability to diverse deployment scenarios[11].

Platforms like Hugging Face play a central role in this ecosystem by providing a collaborative hub for accessing, evaluating, and deploying open-source models. The Hugging Face Model Hub hosts thousands of pre-trained LLMs and provides tools for inference, fine-tuning, and integration, making it an essential resource for building scalable and customizable summarization solutions[9].

This project leverages open-source models from Hugging Face[9] and also quantized models deployed locally (via 'llama.cpp'[14] and Hugging Face[20]) or on high-performance inference platforms (CERN's Kubeflow[12] and Groq[8]) and implements a minimal prototype interface designed to align with Indico's native design.

1.1 Objectives

- Develop an intuitive plugin to summarize meeting minutes within Indico.
- Use fully open-source, CPU-compatible models.
- Test more powerful cloud-deployed models for scalable inference.
- Minimize hallucinations and ensure deterministic, reproducible summaries.

1.2 LLM Key Requirements

- Fast inference
- Open-source and license-compatible models
- High-quality outputs
- Support for prompt customization

Figure 1: Plugin/UI flowchart

1.3 Plugin Workflow (UI in Indico)

Goal: let a user generate, review, and optionally save a summary of meeting minutes.

1. **Entry point.** On the event page, the user opens the “Event manage button” dropdown menu and clicks *Summarize*.
2. **Prompt setup.** A modal opens with:
 - a dropdown of *predefined prompts* (incl. “Dev review”, “Grumpy”, “LOL”, “TL;DR”, “Default”, “Old and angry engineer”) and a “Custom” option,
 - a *prompt editor* to tweak or write a custom prompt (with Save/Delete for reuse).

3. **Preview request.** The user hits *Generate summary*. The plugin:
 - (a) disables the form and shows a spinner,
 - (b) sends a GET to the backend `/ai-summary/summarize-event` with *event_id*, *prompt*, and *token*.
4. **Preview rendering.** On success, the modal displays a read-only preview plus:
 - *Save to event* (writes to Event/Notes via backend),
 - *Clear summary* Clears the summary from the preview area.
5. **Save flow.** If the user clicks *Save to event*, the plugin calls `/event/$eventId/api/note` with the source(summary text), render mode(html) and revision id(current revision id). When user goes back to the event page and refreshes the page, the summary is added to the event note.
6. **Failure handling.** For timeouts, auth errors, or empty minutes:
 - the modal shows a concise error banner or error message in the summary preview area,
 - preserves the user's prompt text

2 Methodology and implementation

2.1 Tools and Technologies

- **Frontend:** HTML, JavaScript, React(Semantic UI)[19] integrated into the Indico meeting interface.
- **Backend APIs:** Python-based, interacts with model server.
- **LLMs tested:**
 - ‘llama.cpp’ for quantized local models
 - Hugging Face Transformers pipeline for experimentation
 - CERN Kubeflow for Qwen-32B inference
 - Groq API for ultra-fast testing of LLaMA-3 70B, Gemma 9B, etc.

2.2 Model selection and evaluation

Initially, smaller CPU-compatible models such as `google/flan-t5-large`, `flan-t5-small`, `bart-large-cnn`, and meeting-focused models like `knkarthick/meeting_summary` were tested. While these models were efficient in terms of computational resource usage, the generated summaries were often of low quality. In particular, the outputs contained duplicated sentences, omitted relevant information, and occasionally introduced hallucinated content. To improve consistency across runs, several inference parameters (e.g., `temperature`, `top_k`, `top_p`, and `do_sample`) were tuned, but the overall performance remained inadequate due to model size limitations.

To improve the quality of summaries while maintaining reasonable inference times, quantized models such as `qwen2.5-7b`, `llama-3-8b`, and `mistral-7b` were evaluated using the `llama.cpp` framework. These models provided a better balance between summary quality and computational efficiency; however, their performance was still limited compared to larger-scale models.

Subsequently, several high-performance cloud-based models were evaluated on the Groq platform, including `llama-3-70b`, `qwen-3-32b`, `llama-3.1-8b-instant`, `gemma-2-9b-it`, and `moonshotai-kimi-k2-instruct`. These models achieved high-quality summaries with very low latency (approximately 2 seconds), establishing a performance benchmark for subsequent testing.

Finally, the `Qwen2.5-32B` model, hosted on CERN’s Kubeflow ML platform, was evaluated. It demonstrated strong performance, producing coherent and contextually accurate summaries while maintaining competitive inference times. Given its balance of quality, speed, and integration feasibility, the `Qwen2.5-32B` model was selected for deployment in the current prototype.

Table 1: Comparison of Tested Models for Meeting Summarization

Model	Type / Size	Avg. Inference Time	Evaluation Summary
flan-t5-small / large	Encoder-decoder (small)	~5–7s	Fast but produced low-quality summaries, missing context and introducing duplicates.
bart-large-cnn	Encoder-decoder (medium)	~6–8s	Better than Flan but still struggled with coherence and hallucinations.
knkarthick/meeting_summary	Fine-tuned for meetings	~5s	Optimized for meeting data but underperformed in accuracy and completeness.
qwen2.5-7b / llama-3-8b / mistral-7b	Quantized models	~3–5s	Balanced efficiency and quality but lacked depth compared to larger models.
llama-3-70b / qwen-3-32b / llama-3.1-8b-instant / gemma-2-9b-it / moonshotai-kimi-k2-instruct	Large cloud-hosted models (Groq)	~2s	Delivered high-quality outputs and very low latency; established performance benchmark.
Qwen2.5-32B	Large model (Kubeflow)	~2–3s	Produced coherent, accurate, and context-aware summaries; currently used in the prototype.

2.3 Human-review evaluation

An internal form was created for team-based evaluation of summaries. Criteria included:

- Accuracy
- Summary and format quality
- Avoidance of redundancy

The form remains open; however, models Qwen3-32B, Qwen2.5-32B and moonshotai-kimi-k2-instruct have received the most positive feedback so far.

LLM summary evaluation for meeting minutes

Aug 21, 2025

You'll see different meeting minute samples, and for each one, there are summaries generated by different models. You are invited to rate each summary based on: accuracy, format and summary quality and non-redundancy. Thank you for your time and input!

Start now

2. **Model 2 output:**

Summary
Meeting Summary
Dev Updates

- Fixed bug where repeat_freq is not correctly sent after editing a booking with certain UI elements disabled.
- Updated to dexie v4 and added compound indices to speed up queries.

Bug Fixes

- Fixed some problems pointed out by Adrian.
- Fixed showing custom locations in meeting timetable.

New Features

- Added fields to control the display of recurring weekday/monthly bookings.
- Display accompanying persons in the registration.

Indico Integration

- New Checkin app API on the Indico side ready to merge.
- Small microservice to aggregate public indico API responses for multiple categories.

Miscellaneous

- Resolve typo in the installation guide.
- Default speakers_can_submit to true for new events.

Processing Time: 135 seconds

	1(low)	2	3	4	5(high)
Format quality	<input type="radio"/>				
Accuracy	<input type="radio"/>				
Summary quality	<input type="radio"/>				
Non-redundancy: 1 (low) – contains repeated information; 5 (high) – free from repetition.	<input type="radio"/>				

Figure 2: Human evaluation form example

3 Prototype in action

Current implementation[6] includes:

- Plugin architecture
- UI integration (Summarize button + predefined prompt dropdown + prompt editor + summary preview)
- Save custom prompt and manage saved prompts(Delete option)
- Accessing qwen 2.5 32b model which is hosted on CERN Kubeflow platform via API
- Save the returned summary to the event note
- Clear the summary from the preview area

Figure 3: Event page

Figure 4: Summarize item added to dropdown options

Summarize Meeting

Select Prompt
Choose a predefined prompt, edit, or create a custom one

Default

Manage Saved Prompts

Preview of prompt sent to the model (editable)

You are a precise assistant that summarizes meeting minutes accurately and clearly. Stick to the facts. Do not add opinions, assumptions, or inferred content.

Instructions:

- Use concise bullet points, grouped into clearly named sections.
- Avoid assumptions or repetition.
- Ensure the summary is easy to scan and logically structured.

Generate summary

Preview
Summary

No summary yet

Figure 5: Summary modal

Summarize Meeting

Select Prompt
Choose a predefined prompt, edit, or create a custom one

Default

Default

TL;DR

Dev minutes (group by project)

Grumpy

Old and angry engineer

LOL

Custom...

Generate summary

Figure 6: Predefined prompt options

Select Prompt
Choose a predefined prompt, edit, or create a custom one

Custom...

Manage Saved Prompts

Custom prompt

This is a really good custom prompt. pretend it is. write somethingsomethingsomethingsomething.....
Summarize this meeting with this format below: ...

Save Custom Prompt

Preview of prompt sent to the model (editable)

This is a really good custom prompt. pretend it is. write somethingsomethingsomethingsomething.....
Summarize this meeting with this format below: ...

Generate summary

Select Prompt
Choose a predefined prompt, edit, or create a custom one

This is a really good custom p...

Manage Saved Prompts

Preview of prompt sent to the model (editable)

This is a really good custom prompt. pretend it is. write somethingsomethingsomethingsomething.....
Summarize this meeting with this format below: ...

Generate summary

Manage Saved Prompts

This is a really good custom prompt. pretend it is. write somethingsomethingsomethingsomething..... Summarize this meeting with this format below: ... Delete

Close

Manage Saved Prompts

No saved prompts yet.

Close

Figure 7: Custom prompt, option to save or delete the prompt

Summarize Meeting

Select Prompt
Choose a predefined prompt, edit, or create a custom one

Dev minutes (group by project)

Manage Saved Prompts

Preview of prompt sent to the model (editable)

You are a precise assistant that summarizes development meeting minutes accurately and clearly. Stick to the facts. Do not add opinions, assumptions, or inferred content. The input contains updates categorized under headers such as Dev and Misc, with emojis indicating the type of update (e.g. Status: 🔄 WIP | 🚧 Under Review | ✅ Merged; Types: 🐛 Bugfix | 🚀 Feature/Improvement | 📄 Internal change | 🔒 Security).

Instructions:
- Group updates by project or module (e.g., Newdle, Indico, Check-in App, Room Booking/Burotel).

Generate summary

Preview
Summary

Newdle

- Replaced (deprecated) node-sass with dart-sass (#455)
- Updated from Node 16 to Node 20 (#457)
- Included comment on answer exports (PR: #454)
- WIP: Adding CSV writer for answer exports (PR: #456)

Check-in App

- Enabled service worker for the PWA which handles caching and updates
- Added workaround for a bug in IndexedDB on Firefox which breaks compound indexes

Indico

- WIP: Adding an option to anonymize users (#5838)
- Set speakers can submit to true as the default (PR: #6025)
- WIP: Improving timeline notifications to editors/authors
- WIP: Working on Jinja templates

Room Booking/Burotel

- UI elements override to permit recurring weekly/monthly bookings under review (PR: #6017)
- Adding fields to toggle display of recurring bookings under review (PR: #151)
- List of bookings for user + cloning booking (Issue: #6009)

Save summary Clear summary

Figure 8: Example output from the summary generator using dev minutes prompt

Summarize Meeting

Select Prompt
Choose a predefined prompt, edit, or create a custom one

Grumpy

Manage Saved Prompts

Preview of prompt sent to the model (editable)

Your persona: You hate your job, and you hate meetings, and you want to make everyone know about this when summarizing the nonsense you had to work on last week.

Format each section like this:
Section Title
- First bullet point
- Second bullet point
Now, summarize the following meeting minutes:

Generate summary

Preview
Summary

Dev Work Highlights

- Fixed a bug where the wrong language was used for some email notifications in the 3.2.x version
- Ensure session materials are included in the material package for distributors
- Successfully merged Python 3.12 support, adding yet another feature to a system no one cares about
- Addressed various issues and improvements related to the new check-in API, because fixing bugs is just a joy (not)

Miscellaneous Activities

- Demonstrated the room booking functionality to a Labotel representative, who found it decent enough, considering we're trying to hire them for something that should be trivial
- Room manager side functionality was deemed satisfactory, though not exactly groundbreaking

Ongoing Projects

- Are we working on the initial pull request #6017 to override UI elements for recurring weekly/monthly bookings
- Working on Burotel Plugin additions, specifically to toggle display options for recurring bookings (PR #151)
- Trying to compile a comprehensive list of bookings for users and enable booking cloning, tackling issue #6009

Newly Initiated Projects

- Putting in the effort to replace the deprecated package (node-sass) with dart-sass following the developments in #455
- Attempting to transition from Node 16 to Node 20. The hope is that this switch will somehow magically enhance our productivity, but we'll see (#457)
- Enabled the service worker for our Progressive Web App (PWA) to handle caching and updates, big whoop
- Implemented a workaround for a Firefox-specific IndexedDB bug, which means we now have a special fix for a browser that's somewhat unpopular and on a fringe browser issue

Indico Updates

- On the lookout for an option to anonymize users, part of the 3.3 roadmap (Issue #5838)
- Adjusted the default setting to allow speakers to submit their content
- Smoothed out some formatting issues like a pro, while also breathing new life into timeline notifications for editors and authors
- We're in the thick of working on Jinja templates, though it's not exactly thrilling

This week was [inset lengthy rant about how uneventful and frustrating meetings/development tasks are], but I suppose at least we were busy, or at least busy pretending to get things done.

Save summary Clear summary

Figure 9: Grumpy prompt and summary

test
✎

📅 Friday Aug 1, 2025, 3:00 PM → 5:00 PM Europe/Zurich

Description description

Summary

Dev Work Highlights

- Fixed a bug where the wrong language was used for some email notifications in the 3.2.x version
- Ensure session materials are included in the material package for distribution
- Successfully merged Python 3.12 support 🎉, adding yet another feature to a system no one cares about
- Addressed various issues and improvements related to the new check-in API, because fixing bugs is just a joy (not)

Miscellaneous Activities

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- Adjusted the default setting to allow speakers to submit their content
- Smoothed out some formatting issues like a pro, while also breathing new life into timeline notifications for editors and authors
- We're in the thick of working on Jinja templates, though it's not exactly thrilling

This week was [insert lengthy rant about how uneventful and frustrating meetings/development tasks are], but I suppose at least we were busy, or at least busy pretending to get things done.

🕒 8/26/25, 3:39 PM 👤 Zeynep Caysar

Figure 10: Saved grumpy summary to event page

Summarize Meeting

Select Prompt
Choose a predefined prompt, edit, or create a custom one

LOL

Manage Saved Prompts

Preview of prompt sent to the model (editable)

Imagine you're a stand-up comedian summarizing a meeting. Stick to the facts. End with a mic-drop line. Be concise, brief and humorous. Now, summarize the following meeting minutes:

Generate summary

Preview
Summary

Alright folks, let me take you through the meeting where we decided to fix a few pesky bugs and add some cool new features. Think of it as our version of a high school reunion, only we're not catching up with old crushes but fixing those pesky emails sending out the wrong language.

First up, we cleared out some email notification snafus, bundled session materials like they're starving for it, and threw in Python 3.12 support like a fresh new shirt! 🎉. Then, we applied some band-aids to the new check-in API and slipped on ruff for linting, 'cause let's face it, sometimes our code looks like we've let the cat walk across the keyboard.

Moving onto the misc side, we gave a demo of room booking functionality to a Labotel enthusiast who seemed to love the standard features so much, he might as well have been proposing. :) And on the Dev front, we're working on letting users make recurring bookings, making the system smarter with PRs flying left and right.

For Newdle, we replaced a deprecated sass package with a fresh new one and ushered in Node version 20 like it's the new cool kid on the block. Speaking of which, the Check-in App now has a service worker managing caching like a champ and has even figured out a workaround for Firefox's INDEXDB funk.

Lastly, for Indico, we're working on anonymizing users, improving timeline notifications, and fixing up some formatting issues, all while crafting those fancy Jinja templates.

And that's a wrap! You heard it here, boys and girls, here at the meeting, we code, we fix, and we leave you with a quote that'll knock your socks off: "Who says we can't make bugs and errors fall in love with being fixed? #devlife" Boom! Mic drop.

Save summary **Clear summary**

Figure 11: Saved funny (debatable) summary to event page

Although the model generally performs well, it occasionally produces hallucinations in Mandarin, as illustrated in the examples below. This is likely related to the fact that the prototype uses the Qwen2.5-32B model, which belongs to the Qwen large language model family developed by Alibaba Cloud, a Chinese company[16].

UI & Booking Enhancements

- Overrode UI elements for endless recurring bookings
📅 习近平，轻松搞定周/月循环预订！
- Toggled display settings for those recurring bookings
– PR approved! 🔥

Figure 12: Hallucination example

Preview

Summary

Alright, folks, gather 'round because I've got the scoop on the latest meeting that was as packed as a sardine can. First up, our developers have pulled a swap-off, ditching Prettier for Biome as their new JavaScript formatter. No more lookin' for your pretties; now it's all about being biome-friendly. Next, they've squashed a bug where JSX files were getting/formatted in a way that would make Picasso scratch his head.

Then, the dev team went on an ESLint binge, adding checks everywhere except ultra-legacy code, meaning your old jQuery-based files are now free of annoying errors, like when grandma finally decides to stop sending chain emails. They've also introduced a `.git-blame-ignore-revs` file, making it so when you blame someone for autoformatting issues, you can blame the void of silence instead.

On the tech side, there's some nifty calendar stuff with Zoom links and iCal metadata being jazzed up to Olympic-level precision. The Ops folks tightened session durations on Indico to a strict 12-hour limit. Took them a while, but better late than never, I suppose.

Meanwhile, the new timetable got some updates to its default contrib duration with cool optimistic UI updates. Say goodbye to laggy refreshes because the UI is now like your favorite restaurant's online ordering system—quick and efficient.

Oh, and not to forget, there's the summer student project 进展得如火如荼，开发了一个Indico插件，还写了openlab报告。而且还在测试某款硬件（条形码扫描器），这可是为了审查一个PR所做的努力。

还有就是，有个同事上周大部分时间外出了，但还是在下雨的日子里完成了部分远程工作。他在支持团队也度过了一个忙碌的星期，目前在等待一些PR的反馈，并且正在完成预定的报告。

爬上最高点，打响掌，仿佛每个人都在努力，做着有意义的事情，就像在海底捞月，但这次是真的捞到了点什么。这真是有点儿意思，这个会议就像是——

...the final act of a Shakespearean play, but with less tragedy and more JavaScript. Mic drop.

Save summary Clear summary

Chinese (detected) ↕ English (American) Options

<p>Oh, and not to forget, there's the summer student project 进展得如火如荼，开发了一个Indico插件，还写了openlab报告。而且还在测试某款硬件（条形码扫描器），这可是为了审查一个PR所做的努力。</p> <p>还有就是，有个同事上周大部分时间外出了，但还是在下雨的日子里完成了部分远程工作。他在支持团队也度过了一个忙碌的星期，目前在等待一些PR的反馈，并且正在完成预定的报告。</p> <p>爬上最高点，打响掌，仿佛每个人都在努力，做着有意义的事情，就像在海底捞月，但这次是真的捞到了点什么。这真是有点儿意思，这个会议就像是——</p>	<p>Oh, and not to forget, the summer student project is in full swing—we've developed an Indico plugin and written an OpenLab report. Plus, we're testing some hardware (a barcode scanner) as part of the effort to review a PR.</p> <p>Also, a colleague was out most of last week but still managed to get some remote work done on rainy days. He also had a busy week with the support team, currently awaiting feedback on some PRs and wrapping up scheduled reports.</p> <p>Climbing to the highest point, clapping hands—it feels like everyone is striving, doing meaningful work, like scooping the moon from the sea, but this time we've actually scooped something up. This is quite interesting; this meeting is like—</p>
---	---

Figure 13: Another hallucination example: sudden switch to Mandarin although the context is correct (Used LOL prompt - maybe it was a joke)

4 Future work

Although the current implementation successfully delivers an end-to-end summarization workflow within Indico, several areas remain open for future improvements to enhance performance, scalability, and overall impact. The following directions outline possible next steps:

- Evaluation with larger models

While smaller Hugging Face models were prioritized during the internship due to limited compute resources and the need for a fast proof of concept, larger models should be re-evaluated. These models may deliver significantly higher-quality summaries, particularly for long and complex meeting minutes.

- Systematic evaluation metrics

At present, evaluation was largely manual and qualitative. Future work should adopt standardized, automatic evaluation metrics such as ROUGE[18], BLEU[1], and F1[3] to provide objective and reproducible measures of summary quality. This would allow more rigorous model comparisons and benchmarking.

- Advanced prompting techniques

The current summarization relies on relatively simple prompts. An important future step is to introduce few-shot examples[4] within prompts to guide the models towards more structured, domain-relevant summaries. This could reduce hallucinations and improve coverage of critical meeting content.

- Multi-turn context summarization

For long meetings spanning multiple sections or topics, implementing multi-turn summarization (e.g., retrieval-augmented generation(RAG)[17]) would preserve context across segments. Instead of truncating or splitting blindly, this approach would allow summaries to remain coherent and informed by earlier discussion.

- Deployability and scalability

Future iterations should focus on building GPU-enabled deployment pipelines, enabling faster inference for larger models. Incorporating these pipelines into platforms such as Kubeflow[12] would ensure scalability, load balancing, and smoother integration with production environments.

- Microservice architecture

The initial design envisioned the summarization logic as a separate microservice decoupled from Indico. Moving further in this direction would keep Indico responsible only for user interaction and request handling, while the summarization backend could evolve independently. This modularity would make the system easier to maintain, upgrade, or replace in the future.

- User Experience Enhancements

In addition to backend improvements, several user-facing features could be introduced to enhance usability:

- Provide options for users to configure the summarization style (e.g., concise, detailed, or bullet-point format).

- Support section-specific summarization, allowing users to focus on relevant sections, such as *Dev review*, while excluding less important content.
- Integrate feedback mechanisms, enabling users to rate summaries and facilitate iterative refinement of the system.

5 Acknowledgements

My nine weeks at CERN have been an incredible journey. I learned so much, from working with open-source LLMs and the Hugging Face platform to exploring plugin architecture and Semantic UI React. CERN is a truly unique place to do an internship, and being part of Indico was very special to me.

Indico plays such an important role in communication at CERN, and it was very exciting to contribute to a platform that is not only used here but also shared with the wider community as open source.

I want to thank my supervisors, Tomáš, Dom, and Adrian, for all their guidance and support. A big thank you as well to my office mates-Ajob, Marina, and Michel-and the entire Indico team for welcoming me, teaching me, and making me feel part of the team from day one. I honestly couldn't have asked for a better group of people to spend these weeks with.

I truly enjoyed every day of this internship, and I'm very grateful for the experience. Thank you!

6 References

- [1] Bleu. *Bleu*. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BLEU> (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [2] CERN. *CERN: the European Organization for Nuclear Research*. URL: <https://home.cern/fr> (visited on 08/21/2025).
- [3] F1. *F1*. URL: <https://datasciencedojo.com/blog/understanding-f1-score/> (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [4] Fewshotprompting. *Fewshotprompting*. URL: <https://www.promptingguide.ai/techniques/fewshot> (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [5] Gemma. *Gemma*. URL: <https://deepmind.google/models/gemma/> (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [6] Github. *Github*. URL: https://github.com/zeynepcaysar/indico-plugins/tree/summary-rebase/ai_summary (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [7] GPT-4. *GPT-4*. URL: <https://openai.com/fr-FR/index/gpt-4/> (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [8] Groq. *GROQ: company that provides fast AI inference in the cloud and in on-prem AI compute centers*. URL: <https://console.groq.com/docs/models> (visited on 08/21/2025).
- [9] Hugging Face. *Hugging Face: open-source model hub*. URL: <https://huggingface.co/> (visited on 08/21/2025).
- [10] Indico. *Indico: open-source event management platform*. URL: <https://indico.cern.ch> (visited on 08/21/2025).

- [11] Jiya Manchanda et al. *opensourceLLM*. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/387140760_The_Open_Source_Advantage_in_Large_Language_Models_LLMs (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [12] Kubeflow. *CERN Kubeflow ML platform*. URL: <https://ml.cern.ch/> (visited on 08/21/2025).
- [13] Llama. *Llama*. URL: <https://www.llama.com/> (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [14] Llamacpp. *Llamacpp: the engine that runs AI models locally*. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Llama.cpp> (visited on 08/21/2025).
- [15] LLMwiki. *LLM*. URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Large_language_model (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [16] Qwen-Hugging Face. *Qwen-HF*. URL: <https://huggingface.co/Qwen> (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [17] RAG. *RAG*. URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Retrieval-augmented_generation (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [18] Rouge. *Rouge*. URL: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ROUGE_\(metric\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ROUGE_(metric)) (visited on 08/27/2025).
- [19] Semantic UI. *Semantic UI React is the official React integration for Semantic UI*. URL: <https://react.semantic-ui.com/> (visited on 08/21/2025).
- [20] TheBlokeHF. *TheBloke: quantized model using GGUF format for open-source models provided in Hugging Face platform*. URL: <https://huggingface.co/TheBloke/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2-GGUF> (visited on 08/21/2025).

